

WOMEN IN MANUFACTURING

Needs and Challenges

DEL 13. Whitepaper

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STRADA PROGRAMME

“Empowering women in manufacturing through leadership development”

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STRADA PROGRAMME

STRADA is a project of EIT Manufacturing, co-funded by the European Union.

STRADA Women in Manufacturing is a leadership programme designed, piloted and implemented in 7 European countries (Spain, Italy, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Estonia, Lithuania and Ireland), targeted to female MSc and PhD students in engineering and women employed in manufacturing. The leadership programme combines mentorship with training on innovation, entrepreneurship, digitisation and management. The programme includes networking opportunities and career development coaching.

STRADA partners represent various areas of the manufacturing ecosystem: Research Performing Organisations, SMEs, MNCs and Academia, bringing their experience in leadership and innovation to the programme.

The project runs from January to December 2023 and involves nine partners: *CTAG (Automotive Technology Center of Galicia) (Spain), LINPRA (Lithuania), Politecnico di Torino (Italy), University College Dublin (Ireland), University of Tartu (Estonia), Whirlpool (Italy), Fablab (Bosnia and Herzegovina), Cleantech (Bulgaria) and Nightingale HQ Limited (Ireland).*

EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMME:

STRADA aims to provide women in manufacturing environments with the necessary skills to start and grow their own businesses or develop their professional careers, whether in academia or industry, rising to management and leadership positions.

This paper is a needs analysis of the target audience (female students in MSc and PhD degrees leading to manufacturing positions, women employed in manufacturing) whether in academia, RTOs or industry.

The programme works with these women to design and execute an action plan for change through:

- specific training
- networking events
- personalized mentorship.

The programme offers:

- selected modules
- nuggets via Skills.move
- webinars

for participants and other women in the network.

More information is available at the following website: <https://stradawomen.eu/> or writing to info@stradawomen.eu.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The goal of this White Paper is to understand the needs and challenges of women within the manufacturing sector. The results of the analysis, mainly conducted through surveys and interviews, will be used as a basis to develop a structured Leadership Programme focussed on empowering women. In particular, attention is placed on the current conditions of women within the sector and the need to improve their working and living conditions and to cover relevant roles and responsibilities.

This document provides inputs for programmes aimed at eliminating gender disparities in the manufacturing sector. Women will receive suggestions on how to have greater engagement in manufacturing, promote their empowerment and ensure that the manufacturing sector is equally accessible for women in terms of their skills and competencies.

Moreover, recommendations will be provided for organisations in relation to reducing gender discrimination and giving women opportunities for career growth.

The results shown represent the basis for organisations to reduce gender inequality in manufacturing and to facilitate women's careers in the sector. This paper provides inputs that can guide the implementation of a programme which includes training, mentorship sessions, dedicated webinars and courses. It also recognizes the need for active engagement from managers, recruiters, teachers, trainers, and society as a whole to achieve these goals.

2. CONTEXT

Gender equality is an important issue within the European economy. Recent studies have found gender inequality to be an impediment to economic growth, stressing the robustness of the link between poverty reduction and gender equality^{1,2}. Reducing gender inequality is a driver for achieving the first Sustainable Development Goal (SDG1 – UN) of ending poverty in all its forms everywhere. Moreover, achieving gender equality is key to improving prosperity for everyone. In the European economy, roles like CEO (Chief Executive Officer), COO (Chief Operating Officer) or CFO (Chief Financial Officer) are mainly occupied by men; only 19% of European companies have a woman in one of these positions, according to the Gender Diversity Index 2020, produced by European Women on Boards³.

Despite this underrepresentation, women have already demonstrated their value in the workplace. There are studies which show the added value that women can bring to the development and success of companies. For instance, a study from Zenger Folkman demonstrates that while men score high on technical and professional expertise and developing a strategic perspective, women excel at taking initiative, displaying resilience, practicing self-development, driving for results, displaying high integrity and honesty, and developing others⁴. In addition to that, the report published by the Credit Suisse Research Institute (CSRI), Gender 3000, illustrates a positive correlation between increased gender diversity in leadership positions and superior returns on capital, Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) and stock performance. The more pervasive diversity is within an organization, the stronger the relationship⁵.

Gender inequality is prevalent in the manufacturing sector, a result of many complex factors such as old prejudices and women's preferences for non-STEM subjects. The negative perception of manufacturing jobs has contributed greatly to the skills gap, but if that attitude can be changed it will be beneficial to the entire industry.

In addition to the above factors, we cannot ignore the impact and the consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic. In fact, it has caused job losses in the manufacturing sector, particularly impacting part-time and temporary workers. A significant share of this category of workers are women. This stems from the historical difficulty for women in negotiating job contracts with better terms or provisions compared to male counterparts. This situation calls for solving a much bigger issue, which is the lack of inclusion of women in manufacturing.

¹ Neves, P.C., and Silva, S.M.T. (2014). Inequality and Growth: Uncovering the Main Conclusions from the Empirics. *The Journal of Development Studies*, vol. 50, No. 1, (November), pp. 1–21.

² Hakura, D., Hussain, M.; Newiak, M.; Thakoor, V.; Yang, F. (2016). Inequality, Gender Gaps, and Economic Growth: Comparative Evidence for Sub-Saharan Africa. IMF Working Paper. Available from <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WP/Issues/2016/12/31/Inequality-Gender-Gaps-and-Economic-Growth-Comparative-Evidence-for-Sub-Saharan-Africa-43946> (Accessed 18 February 2018).

³ <https://europeanwomenonboards.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/Gender-Equality-Index-Final-report-2020-210120.pdf>

⁴ <https://hbr.org/2019/06/research-women-score-higher-than-men-in-most-leadership-skills>

⁵ <https://www.credit-suisse.com/about-us-news/en/articles/media-releases/credit-suisse-gender-3000-report-shows-women-hold-almost-a-quart-202109.html>

How to break down the barriers

The negative perception of the manufacturing sector could be reduced by improving education. Innovative approaches could be used, for example:

- Working directly with high school and university level students to change inaccurate judgements about manufacturing - making these jobs more appealing to young men and women.
- Raising awareness amongst educators and parents about the high-quality, well-paid jobs available in manufacturing, helping to break down negative stereotypes.
- Organising mentorship programmes as a key strategy for supporting and retaining students, young scientists, and engineers in STEM fields.
- Creating opportunities for young girls to get hands-on experience in STEM fields. Increasing the amount of positive exposure when girls are young will increase their knowledge of opportunities in manufacturing later in life.
- Events such as webinars and conferences, which showcase the benefits of a career in manufacturing.

To address a lack of inclusion, stronger gender policies in the manufacturing environment and overcoming gender stereotypes are required to reduce the pay gap and provide women with better working terms and conditions.⁶

The manufacturing sector should leverage women in leadership positions who become role models for others and play a crucial role in building an inclusive workplace culture which attracts and retains top talent. Thus, organizations should work to increase the number of highly talented women in relevant positions, as a strategic priority for improving business performance and building an inclusive culture - and not simply as a diversity initiative or a box to be ticked.

Following this direction, the STRADA project aims to promote collaboration among different kinds of organisations within the manufacturing sector, and to encourage female leaders to train and inspire other women, in order to eliminate the most significant barriers to change and implement diversity strategies that will accelerate progress. The following analysis of women's challenges and needs represents the basis for the development of a programme that can make the difference in addressing the requests and problems of women in manufacturing.

⁶ BACK TO THE FUTURE: MANUFACTURING BEYOND COVID-19. KEY FINDINGS FOR A RESILIENT MANUFACTURING SECTOR IN THE NEW NORMAL . World Manufacturing Forum 2020.

3. ANALYSIS OF CHALLENGES AND NEEDS

The study was carried out using the following approach:

1. Identification of women target groups: the aim was to identify the categories of women that should be targeted by the STRADA programme.
2. Online survey: the aim of the survey was to collect data on the current situation of women in manufacturing.
3. Face-to-face interviews: the aim was to collect experience and personal feedback/perception from women working or willing to work in the manufacturing sector.

In the following sections, each of these actions is addressed, reporting the results of the activity and the feedback collected.

3.1 TARGET WOMEN

The manufacturing sector involves the employment and engagement of people from different kinds of organisations and at different levels. This study considers all the categories that have a role in the development of the sector, including academia and industry.

Based on this view, four main target groups were considered, and for each one specific sub-categories, as reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Target groups of women for STRADA programme

Target Group Name	Sub-category Name	Sub-category ID
University	Master student	A-1
	PhD student	A-2
	Researcher/Teaching staff	A-3
	Professor	A-4
Industry	Junior (until 3 years of experience)	B-1
	Senior /Manager (from 4 to 30 years of experience)	B-2
	Director (of department/function)	B-3
	Entrepreneur (Founder of a company/CEO)	B-4
Research Center	Researcher	C-1
Association	Employee	D-1

3.2 RESULTS FROM ONLINE SURVEY

A survey was developed and published through STRADA social media (LinkedIn, Website, STRADA partners' newsletters) and events were organized by the project partners in order to collect as many answers as possible and best understand the current situation for women in the manufacturing sector. The survey was answered by 53 people of which 50 declared to be women, 2 to be men and 1 preferred not to specify.

The profile of the survey participants is reported in the following graphs.

Figure 1: Participants' gender

Figure 2: Participants' nationality

Figure 3: Organisations to which the participants belong

Figure 4: Share of men and women in the participants' working place

The participants were asked to express their perception of discrimination in career development, and their perception of different factors that can negatively impact career development. The feedback is reported in the following graphs.

Perception of discrimination in career development (%)

Figure 5: Perception of discrimination in career development

perception of FACTORs that can impact the career development

Figure 6: Perception of factors that can negatively impact career development

In addition, they were asked to express their opinion on possible prejudices within the manufacturing sector, as reported below.

Table 2: Participants' opinion on possible prejudices in the manufacturing sector*

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree or disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	I do not know
Women can learn technical things, but it does not come natural as for men.	26	17	4	1	4	1
It is just as important to most women as it is for men to have a successful career	/	1	1	11	37	3
The career in the manufacturing sector is more suitable for men than for women	23	11	7	8	3	1
Men have more business acumen than women	33	9	5	2	1	3
In general, men and women are equally represented in senior/decision-making positions in manufacturing sector	9	25	5	9	1	4
Women have to perform better than men to be considered in their job	2	6	2	20	19	4
My department is committed to promote gender equality	1	4	13	15	16	4

*answers in absolute values

The survey also sought to better understand the needs and challenges of women in the manufacturing sector.

Challenges:

The following question was posed to the participants: *Which challenge are you facing in developing your career in the manufacturing sector?* The following answers were collected.

- Conservative stereotypes and narrow-minded approaches;
- Low consideration of women as potential candidates for specific roles in the organization;
- Stereotypes outside of the company, i.e. by customers, suppliers, partners, etc.;
- Difficulty of multidisciplinary;
- Difficult to balance personal life and effort required by the organization;
- Difficult to access professional opportunities as they are 'locked in' to people (mostly men) who have been viewed as the leader of a certain domain for a long time;
- Difficult to find job opportunities;
- Difficult to grow in current job position;
- Education and background not wanted in the manufacturing sector;
- Being a woman can be a problem: no solutions for this ;
- Low salaries.

Needs:

The following question was posed to the participants: *What do you need to develop your career in the manufacturing sector?* The following answers were collected.

- Courses and programmes which improve skills and competencies;
- Opportunities for increasing digital skills;
- Support and encouragement to increase self-confidence;
- Success stories: the topic of women in manufacturing is associated by the media with issues, challenges, problems and other kinds of negative experiences. Thus women tend not to pursue manufacturing as a career as it is positioned as problematic. Success stories would motivate women;
- Mentorship, autonomy and a career plan;
- Practice: women need to prove to others that they are able to manage the same work as men. More experience of this within a manufacturing environment may help;
- Growth opportunities, training, recognition;
- Higher salaries;
- Opportunities for networking at national and international level.

3.3 RESULTS FROM FACE-TO-FACE INTERVIEWS

Face-to-face interviews were conducted for this study. Women were selected from different organisations and countries, in order to cover the identified target groups (see Table 1) (at least 2 interviews for each target group were conducted). Some highlights from the interviews are reported below. Only the target group is indicated; no additional information about the participants is reported, in compliance with Regulation EU no. 2016/679 - General Data Protection Regulation, "GDPR".

Voices of Women from University

Master student – Cat A1

*“..men feel more knowledgeable about study topics than women.
I would like to work in a large company, specifically on activities concerning industrial production processes. Being a woman could negatively influence career development.
I would need more incentives from companies regarding professional development. More attention from companies regarding the possibility of continuing training in the company after the academic experience, perhaps through participation in master on specific topics...”*

PhD student – Cat A2

*“..my research is at the core of the future of manufacturing, with digitization of manufacturing being a hot topic..
There are no female role model in my area so it is difficult to project oneself into a career – There are very few women with same background in leadership positions in academia.
I sometimes feel that people around me wonder what a woman (me) is doing in focusing the research on manufacturing. It has never been expressed openly but I can perceive it from the questions people ask me, at work and outside work.
I need to develop my confidence, learning what leadership is about and if it is for me! What would really help my career is to have a better understanding of career options in my area.”*

Associate Professor – Cat A3

*“..We are in 6 female on a total of 35 academics. When I was student, I realized that I was not invited to some social events, which I did not perceive as discriminatory, but just unease at how to do things with one female colleague onboard!
Work-life balance is definitely a challenge with small children at home, so I needed to be more realistic with professional ambition.
Being a mother of young children has impacted my career path, slowing down the promotion path (fewer publications, less time for research, etc.).
Courses/programmes for women’s career developments – in my opinion - are useful, because they are concrete, personalised, direct advice vs talk shop.”*

Professor – Cat A4

"..In my department we are 35% women (50 years old), 65% men (60 years old). Men feel more secure, women have some uncertainties which come out in some cases with a more cautious attitude, and in other cases by being very independent and autonomous.

I choose to work in University firstly because of passion for additive manufacturing topics and the possibility of innovation in this area; secondly, because of work management aspects such as flexible working hours.

Among my challenges, one concerns the conciliation of work and life, i.e., the ability to maintain well-being at both a professional and family level. Moreover, having children influences the timing, because research activity, especially in the laboratory, slows down or has to be interrupted. Since researchers are evaluated on the results of their research, having children has a negative impact on career development, leading to a slowdown. Consequently, when you want to have children (especially for women), you have to consider the repercussions you may have professionally.."

Voices of Women from Industry

Junior - Cat B1

"..I work in an office with 90% men and 10% women (average age is 45). By some male colleagues, I feel that they do not take me seriously. Within our department I receive the right support on time. However, sometimes there are difficulties to reach out colleagues from other departments because they don't take serious my requests.

Regarding the age, it is difficult to find a job when you are young and an employer wants a worker with a lot of experience. The main challenge for me now is to find the right role where I will be satisfied with my responsibilities and job I do.."

Senior/Manager - Cat B2

"..In my department we are 96% Men and 4% Women, with good relations among them. My company evaluates people for their skills and competences in an objective way. I always demand a lot from myself and my dream was always to be in a technical role connected with production. The best support I can receive is the continuous presence of a boss from whom I can learn something every day.

One of my challenges is to demonstrate that technical roles can also be handled by young women, with good and better results. Age and Gender are the most common biases for Italian senior manager roles. I'm not a feminist but a woman needs to demonstrate always more than a man to be professionally recognized. I don't have specific needs because I'm really satisfied with my career path.."

Senior/Manager - Cat B2

"..I belong to an engineering department since the beginning of my career when only 3 women were working there.

I felt a strong discrimination at the beginning of my career when I communicated to my department director (at that time) that I was pregnant. His reaction was very strong and negative and he clearly communicated to me that this was not compliant with an engineer career in the company ... "good mothers stay at home with children". Fortunately, this "old style approach" has been abandoned during the following years and now we see manufacturing directors who are in the same time happy mothers. My career is actually not at the same level than my male peers and this is a fact. The balance of the workload and family load with my husband changed my priorities in a way that was not compliant with company requirements at the beginning of my career. Currently, my company seems not available to offer me something more, probably due to age (I think, it considers 40 years as the final deadline of a career path).

Director - Cat B3

"..I have direct and friendly relations with my colleagues. There are differences in relations based on people personalities not related to gender criteria.

I have also had to deal with many people who welcomed me with pre-existing biases, judgements and surprise, as if I happened to be there by chance and as someone that is "outside the box".

I have always tried to overcome this by demonstrating my true personality, professionalism and my passion for the job I do. I always say and support other women in believing in themselves and strive for the best results and ambitions in their job. I am able to cope with both work, wife and mother responsibilities with help of flexible working hours and family support as well. At this point of my life my professional choices has to be in line with my family life balance..."

Entrepreneur/CEO - Cat B4

"I started in 1999 and built my professional path in manufacturing companies, till 2018. Then I started my entrepreneurial journey, in digital and investments.

In manufacturing, I had to be three times better and better performing than men in the same position, in order to emerge and grow. I have sacrificed my time and my life. I had some frustration due to the extra effort to reach career step and due to men behavior in some circumstances. Currently, the only factor that influences the development of my career is gender.

I see a gender gap in the manufacturing sector: since very few women study engineering, we miss them in corporates. We need a cultural shift that can be enabled by diversity, diversity of vision and experience. Diversity is a crucial value.

Voice of Women from Research Center

Researcher - Cat C1

"..We are 33% women (31 years on average), 66% men (32 years on average). Relations with colleagues are positive and collaborative. No difference between men and women.

I decided to pursue a career as a researcher because I wanted to develop something new and innovative. Gender does not influence career development. One factor that does influence career development to some extent is age. Relationships with foreign research groups have a lot of influence. Stronger relationships make it possible to deal with different research areas. The younger one is, the more difficult it is to establish international relationships. It would be helpful if there continued to be strong cooperation with companies in the manufacturing sector, at regional, national and international level. These collaborations are necessary since the research activity is mainly based on the needs of companies.."

Voice of Women from Associations

Association employee - Cat D1

"Women make up about 80% of our association and men about 20%, and I have good relations with both men and women. I choose an association because of interesting activities, many projects, and higher salaries.

However, there is still a perceived attitude from male colleagues and managers that women at work are seen as doers but not as equal partners. I notice that sometimes even jobs are assigned on the basis of the fact that you are a woman, not on the basis of your respective competences. Age, having children and gender are the most influential factors in career development. Obviously, it is more likely to be a young, childless and preferably male worker."

4. OVERVIEW AND RECOMMENDATIONS

4.1 UNIVERSITY WOMEN

The presence of females in faculties related to manufacturing and engineering is low due to the low proportion of girls and young women choosing STEM subjects. The general challenge for universities is how to attract women when there is high competition from other faculties.

Women have many challenges that make their life in university difficult. Different categories talk about specific challenges and needs.

Master students find it difficult to correlate the knowledge acquired from different courses to a mindset capable of dealing with the problems that arise in a manufacturing work context. A second challenge is the short time available, which makes the first challenge even more complex.

PhD students say that publication chasing is stressful, especially when it is not related to experiments; it is a lot harder to publish. The absence of female role models in leadership positions makes it difficult to project oneself into a career. There is also a perception that a woman is out of place doing research in manufacturing.

PhD students also noted that career development may be influenced by the choice of EU country; northern countries offer more opportunities compared to southern countries. Moreover, the number of working hours at university can be too long for a woman who wishes to have children.

Researchers/Teaching staff struggle with challenges more related to the management of work-life balance. Having children brings women to be more realistic with professional ambition; managing family life slows down the promotion path. Moreover, they also face limited opportunities for promotion and uncertainty of the future, which adds pressure on their daily job. Very often, they need to speak up to be heard in a male dominated environment and they work hard to secure funding for conducting research.

Thus, a factor that significantly influences their career is leave entitlements (e.g. maternity leave) which is definitely an obstacle to career progression and profile growth, in addition to the difficulties of juggling child care and work. Moreover, the limited number of career opportunities does not allow professional growth.

Professors also talk about the difficulty to balance work and life, i.e. the ability to maintain well-being at both a professional and family level. They say that having children can significantly influence career development because it reduces the time available for research and other academic activities.

RECOMMENDATIONS for Universities

- *Support women to develop self-confidence and leadership skills;*
- *Orient and guide students to make them aware of the career options after a PhD;*
- *Create opportunities for networking with people from both academia and industry;*
- *Create opportunities for students for continual training, including within industry;*

- *Encourage the development of manufacturing equipment more suitable for women's needs (currently men have an advantage with very heavy equipment);*
- *Organise courses/programmes/training for women's career development and leadership;*
- *Pursue gender equality in the workplace;*
- *Encourage work-life balance and the opportunity for women to hold managerial positions.*

4.2 INDUSTRY WOMEN

Industry seems to be a more accommodating environment for women in manufacturing compared to university. Companies can offer opportunities to meet women's needs, although there is still a low percentage of women (4% - 15%) working in the manufacturing sector in 2023.

The most significant deviation of this positive trend is revealed at the middle management level, where there can be differences among women in terms of their career. In most cases it depends on the personal path and on the choice to dedicate time to family and children in addition to work. This phenomenon demonstrates how also in an industry environment women are penalised by the choice to have a family and children.

As explained below, there can be different scenarios according to the role level.

Junior profiles are represented by “millennials” that have specific requirements when it comes to work choices. For instance they ask for appropriate salaries, „smart working” (i.e. the possibility to work from a place different from the office), networking opportunities, and nearby working location. And this trend seems to be accentuated for women. They want to take care of family and work at the same time but this does not preclude their ambition to grow professionally. It is evident how companies from the manufacturing sector should open their minds to attract and retain young professionals.

Senior/Manager profiles can have different kinds of experience or approaches according to the role they cover and their ambition. It is possible that some women have the right opportunities to grow and develop their career, especially when Managers and Directors recognise their skills and experience. However, there are some cases in which companies, especially large ones, hold resources without giving opportunities, especially when it comes to women trying to manage work and family life at the same time.

Currently, an improvement is happening where companies do not make distinctions between men and women in terms of career development; women can take managerial roles and also with a lot of success. What is still missing is the ability to attract women to industry and to break down the stereotype that the manufacturing sector is only for men.

Director profiles may sometimes be harmed by negative prejudices or comments on how they achieved the position, or they may be made to feel „outside the box”, while it would be more „natural” for a man to take managerial roles. This means that women have to work harder also to demonstrate their professionalism and passion for the job that is not taken for granted. Motivated by their passion, women in leadership positions also want to inspire and be an example to other women. Being a director does not preclude the possibility of having a family, but a very good work-life balance is needed to manage this.

Entrepreneur/CEO profiles, due to their long experience in the sector, have a more complete picture. They tell about frustrations suffered and sacrifices made to develop their career and to reach manager positions. They had to work more and better than men to emerge and grow. And now that they can make the difference by hiring women, they still see the gender gap because few women approach STEM fields, thus it is difficult to find female resources.

RECOMMENDATIONS for industry

- *Offer appropriate salary to young professionals in order to motivate them;*
- *Offer to young professionals, especially to women, the requested conditions (like smart working, proximity to own location, etc.), to allow them to work and take care of family/children/relatives at the same time;*
- *Foster an open-minded environment where there can be exchange and dialogue among colleagues;*
- *Change the management mindset in order to value the professional experience of women, regardless of gender or age or social status;*
- *Offer new challenges and development programmes, both technical and managerial, that help women to grow and gain more experience.*

4.3 RESEARCH CENTRE WOMEN

Women operating in research centres are not encountering difficulties related to gender. They talk about age as an influencing factor. In order to do research, collaboration with foreign research groups is very important to be able to deal with different research areas. However, young researchers have difficulties establishing these international relationships.

In general, with regards to research centres, women feel protected and gender does not influence career development.

RECOMMENDATIONS for Research centers

- *Identify research groups and companies at a regional, national and international level to collaborate with;*
- *Support and encourage collaboration with foreign research groups and with companies in the manufacturing sector;*
- *Create networking opportunities.*

4.4 ASSOCIATIONS WOMEN

Women in associations declared a high percentage of women in working positions, but this does not help to remove the old attitude from men regarding the career development of women. Women working in

associations suffer the same problems as women in industry or university. They do not receive appropriate recognition or salaries, and having children is one of the factors that most influence their careers.

RECOMMENDATIONS for Associations

- *Encourage men to support women in performing their job;*
- *Promote a friendly working environment, to avoid women being marginalised;*
- *Recognize and value women competencies and assign tasks accordingly;*
- *Introduce a clear evaluation method for both managers and employees;*
- *Recognize the achievements of women;*
- *Implement transparent salary scales.*

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study shows how the involvement and integration of women in the manufacturing sector is happening, but a lot of work still has to be done. The current scenario can be improved if organisations and female leaders take action to meet women's needs. Universities, companies and research centres can leverage women in leadership roles to understand what women need, what can be done, and also to inspire new women to pursue a career within the sector.

In general, a more balanced and inclusive manufacturing sector is required to allow women to start and continue their careers, and to be able to manage the responsibilities of personal life and working life. This change should begin at the time of education, when women need to know about the opportunities that available are for them in the manufacturing sector. It seems that few women are attracted by the manufacturing sector, and if they are and they start, they encounter various difficulties, especially if they decide to continue their career in an academic environment. On the other hand, the situation seems to be better within industry where flexibility is offered to women in order to find the right balance between work and personal life. Despite this, companies still have to make their working environments more attractive and offer growth opportunities, considering that the proportion of women is very low (around 30%).

The STRADA project is doing crucial work to offer new opportunities to women in the manufacturing sector at a European level. Networking occasions, webinars lead by senior female leaders, sharing advice and experience, a training programme dedicated to young women; all these activities will have a relevant impact on European women who are interested to know what the manufacturing sector can offer, and what are the strategies and paths that can be followed.

FEATURED PARTNERS

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CLEANTECH
BULGARIA

NightingaleHQ

